

Supporting Information

Hold this in place: Continuous, crystalline Sb_2S_3 ultrathin light absorber coatings in solar cells based on photonic concentric p-i-n heterojunctions

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Figure S1: SEM image of the dewetting behaviour of Sb_2S_3 on an alkyl-terminated FTO/ TiO_2 surface, achieved by pulsing TTIP in the ALD before overgrowth with Sb_2S_3 without breaking vacuum. The Sb_2S_3 dewetts during thermal annealing to form crystalline stibnite spheres on the surface.

Figure S2: SEM images of the dewetting behaviour of 35 nm Sb_2S_3 on Si/ SiO_2 wafers a) without ZnS interfacial layer showing, b) with 1 nm ZnS and c) without ZnS but overgrown with 20 nm of ZnO and etched after annealing. Both the ZnS interfacial layer and the ZnO capping layer succeed to prevent Sb_2S_3 dewetting.

Figure S3: Optical microscopy images of ZnS/Sb₂S₃ films on Si wafers recorded without polarization filter. a) ZnS/Sb₂S₃ as grown. b) ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO as grown. c) ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO as grown and etched. d) ZnS/Sb₂S₃ annealed. e) ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO annealed. f) ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO annealed and etched.

Figure S4: Optical microscopy images of annealed ZnS/Sb₂S₃ films on Si wafers recorded without (center) and with polarization filter at various rotation angles. The contrast observed is due to crystal orientation.

Figure S5: Optical microscopy images of annealed ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO films on Si wafers recorded without (center) and with polarization filter at various rotation angles. The contrast observed is due to crystal orientation.

Figure S6: Optical microscopy images of annealed ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO films on Si wafers after removal of the ZnO capping layer by etching recorded without (center) and with polarization filter at various rotation angles. The images were recorded at the same location on the same sample as in SI Fig. 5. The contrast observed is due to crystal orientation.

Figure S7: (111) textured silicon pyramids covered with amorphous TiO₂ that were overgrown with ZnS (1 nm) and Sb₂S₃ (35 nm). a) Annealed without ZnO cap, b) Annealed with ZnO cap and c) Annealed with ZnO cap and etched.

Figure S8: SEM top view of annealed ZnS/Sb₂S₃ films in AAO membranes. a) Annealed without ZnO overlayer, showing the formation of Sb₂S₃ nanorods inside the pores and the exposed AAO scaffold surrounding them. b) Annealed with ZnO overlayer and etched, showing a homogeneous coating and open AAO pores.

Figure S9: SEM top views of annealed ZnS/Sb₂S₃ films (15 nm) in TiO₂ nanotubes. a) without ZnO overlayer, showing the clogging of the pores by stibnite crystals and exposed TiO₂. b,c) With ZnO overlayer before (b) and after (c) etching. A homogeneous thin film of Sb₂S₂ is coating the nanotubes.

Figure S10: Representative JV -curves and statistics on interface treatments on annealed ZnS/Sb₂S₃ layers for *Ref* solar cells. a) JV -curves under 1 sun illumination (solid line) and in the dark (dashed line). b) Short circuit current (J_{sc}), c) open circuit potential (V_{oc}), d) fill factor and e) efficiency.

Figure S11: Representative JV -curve and statistics on *Air* solar cells with different annealing temperatures and durations (250°C for 10 min, 300°C for 2 min and 300°C for 30 min). a) JV -curves under 1 sun illumination (solid line) and in the dark (dashed line). b) Short circuit current (J_{sc}), c) open circuit potential (V_{oc}), d) fill factor and e) efficiency. A clear trend of decreasing device performance with increasing annealing temperature and duration is observable.

Figure S12: Representative JV -curves and statistics on planar *Ref* solar cells with different annealing temperatures and durations (250 °C for 10 min, 260 °C for 2 min, 280 °C for 2 min and 300 °C for 2 min). a) JV -curves under 1 sun illumination (solid line) and in the dark (dashed line). b) Short circuit current (J_{sc}), c) open circuit potential (V_{oc}), d) fill factor and e) efficiency. No clear trend of device performance and annealing temperature is observable.

Figure S13: Shunt resistance (R_{sh}) and series resistance (R_s) for different types of solar cells derived from the light (a) and dark (b) JV -curves.

Figure S14: Results of impedance spectroscopy for *Ref*-cells recorded under 1 sun at various potentials approaching V_{oc} . The data points and fit curves are presented in lighter colours for increasing voltages. a) Nyquist plots and b) corresponding Bode-plots.

Figure S15: Results of impedance spectroscopy for *Air*-cells recorded under 1 sun at various potentials approaching V_{oc} . The data points and fit curves are presented in lighter colours for increasing voltages. a) Nyquist plots and b) corresponding Bode-plots.

Figure S16: Results of impedance spectroscopy for $1 \text{ min } O_3$ -cells recorded under 1 sun at various potentials approaching V_{oc} . The data points and fit curves are presented in lighter colours for increasing voltages. a) Nyquist plots and b) corresponding Bode-plots.

Figure S17: Results of impedance spectroscopy for $3 \text{ min } O_3$ -cells recorded under 1 sun at various potentials approaching V_{oc} . The data points and fit curves are presented in lighter colours for increasing voltages. a) Nyquist plots and b) corresponding Bode-plots.

Figure S18: XPS survey of as grown amorphous Sb_2S_3 layers subjected to different durations of UV/ozone treatment. The corresponding HRXPS spectra are shown in Fig. 3 in the main text.

Figure S19: XPS survey (a) and S 2p region (b) of annealed *Ref* ZnS/ Sb_2S_3 layers (green) and annealed and etched ZnS/ Sb_2S_3 /ZnO layers subjected to different durations of UV/ozone treatment (shades of blue). The corresponding HRXPS spectra are shown in Fig. 3 in the main text.

Figure S20: XPS spectra of annealed reference ZnS/Sb₂S₃ layers (green) and annealed and etched ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO layers subjected to different durations of UV/ozone treatment (shades of blue). The layers were subjected to a short ion milling with Ar ions to remove the upper most surface layer. The corresponding spectra before sputtering are shown in Fig. 3 and SI Fig. 19. a) Survey spectrum. b-d) HRXPS of the Sb 3d and O 1s region (b), the S 2p region (c) and the Zn 2p region (d).

Figure S21: XPS spectra of annealed and etched ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO layers (*Air* samples) subjected to different annealing temperature without UV/ozone treatment. a) Survey spectrum. b-d) HRXPS of the Sb 3d and O 1s region (b), the S 2p region (c) and the Zn 2p region (d).

Figure S22: Evolution of composition of the surface of *Air* samples annealed at different temperatures. The Sb 3d peak contributions and the normalized Zn 2p_{1/2} peak intensity show an increase of the Zn signal with increasing annealing temperature while the observed Sb–S to Sb⁰ ratio remains similar.

Figure S23: XPS spectra of *Air* and *1 min O₃* ZnS/Sb₂S₃/ZnO layers that were etched without annealing the capped layer. a) Survey spectrum. b-d) HRXPS of the Sb 3d and O 1s region (b), the S 2p region (c) and the Zn 2p region (d). In the absence of thermal annealing, the Sb–O contribution persists on the *1 min O₃* film surface. The *Air* film shows small quantities of Zn even in the absence of a heat treatment.

Figure S24: High angle annular dark field (HAADF) image and corresponding energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) maps for cross sections *1 min O₃* samples on TiO₂-covered Si wafers. a) HAADF image, b-g) EDX maps for b) Au, c) Zn, d) Sb, e) Ti, f) O and g) S.

Figure S25: HRTEM image of the upper surface of the Sb₂S₃ film in an *Air* sample as shown in Fig. 4 in the main text. Lots of small crystals with various orientations are observable at the Sb₂S₃ / Au interface.

Figure S26: High angle annular dark field (HAADF) image and corresponding energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) maps for cross sections *Air* samples on TiO₂-covered Si wafers. a) HAADF image, b-g) EDX maps for b) Au, c) Zn, d) Sb, e) Ti, f) O and g) S.

Figure S27: Intensity map of the Zn signal of an *Air* sample at the Sb_2S_3 surface.

Figure S28: XPS spectra of ALD-grown ZnO capping layer measured without and with ion milling. a) Survey spectrum. b-d) HRXPS of the O 1s region (b), the C 1s region (c) and the Zn 2p region (d). The ZnO films show significant carbon contamination, even after removal of adventitious carbon by Ar sputtering.

Figure S29: Close-up SEM view of the as-deposited core-shell polymer/ SiO_2 nanospheres on FTO.

Figure S30: SEM top view of FTO/SiO₂^{SP} substrates.

Figure S31: SEM top view (a) and self-correlation image (b) of FTO/SiO₂^{SP} substrates after overgrowth with the ZnO/TiO₂ dual ETM layer.

Figure S32: Representative JV -curve under 1 sun illumination (solid line) and in the dark (dashed line) for a planar $1 \text{ min } O_3$ solar cell with TiO_2 grown by ALD instead of sputtering.

Figure S33: Representative JV -curves and statistics on various ETMs for $1 \text{ min } O_3$ solar cells. a) JV -curves under 1 sun illumination (solid line) and in the dark (dashed line). b) Short circuit current (J_{sc}), c) open circuit potential (V_{oc}), d) fill factor and e) efficiency.

Figure S34: a) SEM top view of $\text{FTO}/\text{SiO}_2^{\text{SP}}/\text{TiO}_2$ substrates as they are used for *Dew.* and TiO_2 cells. b) SEM top view of dewetted $\text{ZnS}/\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_3$ layers (*Dew.*) on $\text{FTO}/\text{SiO}_2^{\text{SP}}/\text{TiO}_2$ substrates.

Figure S35: Polished SEM cross-section of a *sphere* sample employing the ZnO/TiO₂ dual-ETM before etching of the ZnO capping layer. The dashed circle indicates an area that shows local thinning of the sputtered TiO₂ layer on the underside of a nanosphere.

Figure S36: Shunt resistance (R_{Sh}) and series resistance (R_S) for different types of sphere-based solar cells derived from the light (a) and dark (b) JV -curves.

Figure S37: Dark JV -curves in a log-log plot of the different types of 'photonic' solar cells.

Figure S38: 1st derivative of the log-log plot of the dark JV curves revealing the power law relationship in the dark curves for *spheres* and *planar* cells.

Figure S39: a) UV/vis data obtained for Sb_2S_3 and P3HT films on glass. b) Corresponding Tauc-plot derived from the UV/vis data in (a) for Sb_2S_3 and P3HT, assuming a direct allowed transition (exponent $r = 1/2$).

Figure S40: Direct comparison of representative JV -curves for solar cells in planar and structured configuration based on the same dual ETM layer in light (solid lines) and dark (dashed lines).

Figure S41: Mott-Schottky plot of the capacitance-voltage data recorded in the dark at a frequency of 10 kHz. The built-in potentials (V_{bi}) of the respective solar cells are estimated by extrapolating the linear portion of the curve towards zero. Both cell types feature very similar built-in potentials.

Figure S42: Representative EQE spectra with integrated J_{sc} for *planar* solar cells featuring a ZnO/TiO₂ dual-ETM.

Figure S43: Stability of device performance under operation in ambient atmosphere without encapsulation. a) JV -curves under 1 sun illumination at different scan-speeds. b) Evolution of V_{oc} over time. c,d) JV -curves (c) and maximum power point tracking (d) under continuous operation.

Table S1: Summary of average performances and champion efficiencies for types of planar *Ref* solar cells compared in this study.

Cell type	J_{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	V_{oc} [mV]	FF	Efficiency [%]
<i>Ref</i> -type solar cells with different annealing temperature (standard 300 °C, 2 min)				
<i>Ref</i>	14.3 ± 0.6	612 ± 20	0.49 ± 0.01	4.30 ± 0.23
	14	650	0.51	4.64
<i>Ref</i> @250°C (10 min)	13.1 ± 1.1	607 ± 24	0.48 ± 0.02	3.86 ± 0.49
	14.3	630	0.51	4.56
<i>Ref</i> @280°C	14.3 ± 0.9	618 ± 10	0.49 ± 0.01	4.35 ± 0.30
	15.3	630	0.49	4.74
<i>Ref</i> -type solar cells with the crystalline Sb ₂ S ₃ overgrown with ZnO and/or etched with acetic acid				
Etched	12.9 ± 0.8	607 ± 19	0.45 ± 0.02	3.55 ± 0.47
	14.0	620	0.47	4.04
ZnO&Etched	14.4 ± 0.4	636 ± 7	0.50 ± 0.01	4.59 ± 0.23
	14.4	640	0.52	4.82

Table S2: Summary of average performances and champion efficiencies for types of planar solar cells compared in this study that employ ZnO-confined crystallization.

Cell type	J_{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	V_{oc} [mV]	FF	Efficiency [%]
<i>Air</i> -type solar cells obtained by ZnO-confined crystallization at different annealing temperatures without UV/ozone treatment (standard 300 °C, 2 min)				
<i>Air</i>	11.1 ± 0.4	634 ± 17	0.42 ± 0.02	3.00 ± 0.26
	11.5	650	0.44	3.26
<i>Air</i> @250 °C	13.4 ± 0.4	642 ± 18	0.43 ± 0.02	3.73 ± 0.22
	13.2	660	0.46	4.05
<i>Air</i> @300 °C (30 min)	9.4 ± 0.9	558 ± 25	0.38 ± 0.02	1.99 ± 0.31
	10.6	590	0.39	2.46
<i>X min O₃</i> -type solar cells obtained by ZnO-confined crystallization with different durations of UV/ozone treatment (standard 1 min)				
<i>1 min O₃</i>	13.2 ± 0.4	670 ± 10	0.54 ± 0.01	4.81 ± 0.22
	13.9	670	0.55	5.11
<i>3 min O₃</i>	11.4 ± 1.4	471 ± 11	0.43 ± 0.01	2.31 ± 0.35
	13.2	490	0.43	2.79
<i>1 min O₃</i> -type solar cells with different electron transport materials instead of sputtered TiO ₂				
<i>TiO₂ ALD</i>	0.57 ± 0.25	537 ± 15	0.19 ± 0.01	0.059 ± 0.03
	1.03	550	0.19	0.11
<i>ZnO</i>	7.0 ± 0.7	533 ± 24	0.31 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.20
	7.7	580	0.33	1.49
<i>1 min O₃</i> -type solar cells with ZnO/TiO ₂ dual electron transport material				
<i>planar</i>	13.4 ± 0.6	684 ± 7	0.56 ± 0.03	5.13 ± 0.24
	13.6	690	0.57	5.36

Table S3: Summary of average performances and champion efficiencies for the different types of structured solar cells compared in this study.

Cell type	J_{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	V_{oc} [mV]	FF	Efficiency [%]
Structured solar cells with non-close packed SiO ₂ nanosphere scaffold prepared without ZnO-confinement (<i>Dew.</i>) or with ZnO-confinement employing a TiO ₂ ETM (<i>TiO₂</i>) or a ZnO/TiO ₂ dual ETM (<i>spheres</i>)				
<i>Dew.</i>	11.2 ± 1.3	500 ± 25	0.40 ± 0.01	2.23 ± 0.36
	13.0	520	0.40	2.67
<i>TiO₂</i>	12.5 ± 1.6	603 ± 8	0.45 ± 0.01	3.39 ± 0.41
	14.9	610	0.45	4.05
<i>spheres</i>	14.4 ± 1.4	671 ± 18	0.49 ± 0.01	4.74 ± 0.41
	16.8	660	0.49	5.44